

Twofold Mystery (Chongxuan 重玄)

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Chongxuan 重玄 ("Twofold Mystery") is a Daoist teaching developed by early medieval Daoist monastics; the most prominent was Cheng Xuanying 成玄英 (fl. 631-655). The name Chongxuan derives from the fact that the Daoist thinkers, like Cheng Xuanying or Li Rong 李榮 (fl. after 650), used their commentaries to the *Daode jing* 道德經, and specifically to the expression *xuanzhi you xuan* 玄之又玄 in the last sentence of the first chapter, to develop their own version of the four steps of continued negation (also called *si ju* 四句, or tetra lemma), which had become known in China predominantly with Buddhist *Mādhyamika* teachings, as an approach to realize Dao conceptually.// The earliest traces of Chongxuan thought can be found in writings and anecdotes from Daoists active at the courts of the Northern and Southern Dynasties (420-589 CE), it became popular in the early 7th century during the Sui 隋 (581-618 CE) and Tang 唐 (618-907 CE) dynasties in the capital Chang'an. Furthermore, presumably because of individual monks travelling and spreading the new teaching, it spread also in Sichuan. Early 7th century Chang'an saw fierce competition and heated court debates between Buddhists and Daoists. Multi-level interactions between Buddhists and Daoists, from the reading of each other's texts, to the participation in public debates, to the struggle for imperial support and patronage, was most probably the immediate background of the development the intellectual innovations of chongxuan teachings.// Interaction and competition between Buddhists and Daoists gained an important political dimension in the Tang dynasty due to the imperial clan's claim that they, the Li 李 family, were descended from Laozi 老子, whose surname was also said to be Li 李. This claim was an opportunity for the advancement of Daoism, but it required that Laozi (associated in his divinized form with the Celestial Masters tradition dominant in the north) be the principal deity. This was potentially problematic because Daoism, as it was proposed by the clergy of the capital Chang'an, seems to have relied much on the southern tradition of the Three Caverns (a synthesis of the Shangqing 上清, Lingbao 靈寶, and Sanhuang 三皇 traditions), which considered the Heavenly Worthy of Primordial Commencement (Yuanshi Tianzun 元始天尊) to be the highest deity.// To resolve the clash between these two pantheons, Chongxuan theorists turned to the most distinctive feature of their teaching, the use of the logic of the tetra lemma (otherwise known as the four-fold negation from), which they had adapted from the *Madhyamaka* Buddhist tradition. Combining this mode of logic with the Two-Body theory (a Daoist adaptation of the Buddhist theory of the Three Bodies of the Buddha), Chongxuan theorists were able to argue for the logical interpenetration of the Dao, apparently separate deities, and the sage. In doing so, they redefined Laozi and the Heavenly Worthy as "response bodies" (*yingshen* 應身) of the Dao and thus unified the pantheon, making sure Laozi could be treated as the highest deity.// This interpenetration also enabled Chongxuan figures to transfer seemingly anthropomorphic characteristics, such as wisdom and compassion, to the ultimate entity of the Dao, which is inherently devoid of any specific characteristics. They thus defined the Dao as a compassionate entity that actively worked for the salvation of all beings and thereby responded to Buddhist critiques that Daoism did not offer the same type of soteriological benefits as Buddhism.// In fact, Chongxuan theorists developed a sophisticated soteriological model in which individuals could cultivate themselves and return to the Dao, thereby becoming immortal sages. Sages, moreover, were thought to deliberately return from the Dao to the mortal plane (much like a Buddhist *Bodhisattva*) in order to actively work for the salvation of all entities. They did so, it was thought, because they were motivated by the same type of compassion as the Dao.

Date Range: 500 CE - 700 CE

Region: Chang'an, Jiankang, and Sichuan

Region tags: China, Shaanxi Province 陕西省, Jiankang, Xi'an 西安, Chang'an 长安, Sichuan 四川

These were the sites of the most prominent representatives of Chongxuan. Chang'an was a particularly important site as it was the capital of the Tang empire.

参与者的状态

✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

一般变量

成员/团体互动

其他宗教团体与该宗教之间有文化上的接触吗：

一是

Notes: The main representatives of Chongxuan Daoism were in close contact with a variety of other religious groups, including Buddhists, Confucians, and members of popular religious traditions.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 这种文化接触是竞争性的吗：

一是

Notes: A prominent aspect of the courts of the Northern and Southern Dynasties and the Sui-Tang empires was the competition by religious professionals for imperial patronage. Those Chongxuan figures who were present at court thus engaged in frequent competition, particularly with Buddhists, in order to secure patronage for Daoism at the Buddhists' expense. Frequently, these competitions took the form of formal debates between representatives of the Buddhist and Daoist clergy (Assandri 2009, 17-25).

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 文化接触是兼容并包/多元的吗：

一是

Notes: This question is answered "yes" only to indicate that Daoists regarded Buddhists as an alternative, and capable, rival with which they had to compete. As well, Chongxuan Daoists did incorporate certain Buddhist elements, most notably the logic of the tetra lemma, into their own teachings (Assandri 2009, 14-15). However, it is important to emphasize that Chongxuan thinkers did not necessarily view the tetra lemma as a "Buddhist" element that they were accepting, but rather a powerful and universally available tool that could be used in their own theologies.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 文化接触是中立的吗：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ (在采样地区内)有暴力冲突吗：

— 否

Notes: Although there could, at times, be official repressions of different religious groups by the imperial court that were supported by those religious professionals seeking an upper hand over their rivals, there was no direct violence between representatives of Chongxuan Daoism and other groups.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ (与采样地区外的族群)有暴力冲突吗：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

该宗教团体有确认入会的一般性程序/制度吗：

— 否

Notes: Chongxuan adherents were all ordained Daoist clergy and thus went through the usual rituals and procedures of ordination. However, there was no additional process for becoming part of the Chongxuan tradition because it was a teaching, not a defined group.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

宗教团体积极宣教、招募新成员吗：

— 是

Notes: We do not know exactly if religious professionals in early medieval China were mandated to proselytize. However, the monastic manual *Fengdao Kejie*, translated by Livia Kohn (2004) lists five guidelines for ordained Daoists, the third of these stipulates that ordained Daoists should be “using skillful means to guide both Daoists and ordinary people to take refuge [in the Dao]” (Kohn 2004, 110).

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 对宗教专职人员来说，发展信众是强制性的吗：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 所有信徒都必须发展信众吗：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 宗教专职人员必须传道吗：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 所有信众都必须传道吗：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 发展信众是强制的吗：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

宗教有官方的政治支持吗：

— 是

Notes: Chongxuan developed as a Daoist teaching among those Daoists who were present at the courts of the Northern and Southern Dynasties, as well as the Sui and Tang empires. These Daoists were closely affiliated with the imperial clans of the various dynasties of the time of division and the Sui and Tang and engaged in official debates against Buddhists in order to secure official support for institutionalized Daoism over Buddhism (Assandri 2009, 17-25). The Tang dynasty was a particularly advantageous time for Daoists in general, and Chongxuan court Daoists in particular, because the Tang ruling family, the Li 李 clan, claimed descent from Laozi (whose surname was also said to be Li 李). To capitalize on this, Daoists at the time frequently referred to themselves as "the Li family," emphasizing their connection with Laozi and his teachings and, thus, with the imperial clan. This appellation also mirrored the way in which Buddhists referred to themselves as the "Shi family," which evoked the Chinese transliteration (shi 釋) of the Buddha's name, Sākyamuni, "wise man from the Sākyā clan" (Assandri 2009, 196).

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 神职人员由政体出资供养吗：

— 是

Notes: The field does not know much about the finances of Daoism in general, but we can be quite sure that the major temples in the capital, where the most famous Chongxuan thinkers resided, were financed by the court, and that once a religious specialist or priest was invited to reside or take office in one of the state-sponsored temples, his livelihood was also taken care of by imperial patronage. We should note in this context that for example the Benji jing contains passages that explicitly disavow the practice of requiring pledges for scriptural transmission (Assandri 2009, 59), which in other contexts might have served as an independent source of income for Daoist Masters (Strickmann 1977, 27, Schipper 2000, 49).

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 宗教基础设施由政体出资吗：

— 是

Notes: The field does not know much about the finances of Daoism in general, but we can be quite sure that the major temples in the capital, where the most famous Chongxuan thinkers resided, were financed by the court.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 政体首脑和宗教领袖是同一个人吗：

— 否

Notes: We might note however that in the early 7th century, the head of the polity, the emperors Gaozu 高祖 (r. 618-626), Taizong 太宗 (r.626-649) and Gaozong 高宗 (r.650-683) of Tang dynasty, claimed to be descendants of Laozi, who was constructed to be the high deity and founding deity of Daoism by Chongxuan thinkers, especially by Cheng Xuanying.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 政治官员相当于宗教官员吗：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 宗教仪式是由政体强制执行的吗：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 政治律法和宗教法典大致重合：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 政体提供优惠的经济待遇(比如免税)：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

在该宗教中存在叛教的概念吗：

— 是

Notes: We have, with the fierce debates and competition between Buddhists and Daoists, cases of Daoists who converted to Buddhism. Thus, for example, Ji gujin Fo Dao lunheng (T 2104) has a sequel, Xu Ji gujin Fo Dao lunheng (T 2105), which describes a person who converted from Daoism to Buddhism. Another known case is the Buddhist Falin 法琳 (572–640), who converted from Buddhism to Daoism and then back to Buddhism.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 叛教者是否被控诉或惩罚：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

大小和结构

在样本区域中的宗教团体信奉者人数(估计人口，数字)

— 未知领域

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

样本区域中的宗教团体的信奉者数量 (在样本区域人口中的百分比，数字)

— 未知领域

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

宗教团体性质【请选其一】：

— 小型宗教团体（被视作相关的更大的宗教团体的一部分）

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

在该宗教团体中是否存在被认可的领导者：

— 否

Notes: Although there were no formal leaders of Chongxuan, there were particularly prominent representatives with greater influence at court such as Cheng Xuanying and Li Rong.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

经典

宗教团体有经典吗：

经典是一个统称，指的是受到尊崇、与其它文本相比被认为具有特别的权威性和神圣性的文本。严格意义上经典指书写的文本，但是也存在“口述经典”（比如印度的吠陀经典）。

— 是

Notes: In addition to foundational texts such as the Daodejing (and its attached commentaries by prominent Chongxuan theorists like Cheng Xuanying), there were several scriptures that expressed Chongxuan ideas, most notably the Benji jing 本際經 (Scripture of the Original Beginning) and Huming jing 護命經 (Scripture of Saving Life, DZ 19) (Assandri 2009, 49-84). An important general feature of Daoism is the belief that scriptures themselves have supernatural powers and can thus offer protection from harm. These powers come from the scriptures themselves as well as from supernatural beings, Jade Maidens and Jade Lads, who accompany the scriptures and watch over the scriptures and their owners. There are suggestions that this idea of supernatural protection applied to Chongxuan scriptures such as the Benji jing and Huming jing (Assandri 2009, 61-62).

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 它们是书面的吗：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 它们是口述的吗：

— 是

Notes: In addition to a culture of liturgical recitation of important scriptures, Daoism also

featured koujue 口訣, generally secret oral instructions passed on to disciples by their masters during their initiations. Although it is difficult to say for sure in the case of Chongxuan, on account of the fact that many Chongxuan theorists were initiated into the Lingbao tradition, it seems likely that they received such oral teachings.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 经典的来源和一个（或一组）故事有关吗：

一是

Notes: Generally speaking, all (or almost all) Daoist scriptures have stories associated with their origins. Frequently, these stories featured the divine revelation of the scripture in question. For the Daode jing, the key text for Chongxuan teachings, Daoists had developed and embellished a transmission story whose earliest account can be found in Sima Qian's 司馬遷 (145-86 BCE) Shiji 史記 (Records of the Historian) (Kohn and LaFargue 1998, 7-10, Kohn 1998, 255-273). In the case of the Benji jing, another key Chongxuan scripture, the scripture features different narratives and revelations for the different chapters (Assandri 2009, 57-71).

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 由至高无上的神揭示：

一是

Notes: Certain scriptures, such as the Benji jing, are considered revelations of high gods such as the Heavenly Worthy of Primordial Commencement (Assandri 2009, 57-71, where the name is translated as Heavenly Worthy of Primordial Beginning). The Daode jing is an ambiguous case of this because according to the earliest legends reported in Sima Qian's 司馬遷 (145-86 BCE) Shiji (Records of the Historian), it was written and bestowed upon the gatekeeper, Yin Xi 尹喜, by Laozi prior to the latter's departure from the Zhou domain. Depending on perspectives and contexts, Laozi came to be considered a mortal human, a divine being, or a high god manifestation of the Dao itself (worshiped as Taishang Laojun 太上老君 from the Han dynasty onward).

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 由其他超自然生灵揭示：

一是

Notes: Although many scriptures were considered to be revealed, not all of them were ascribed to supreme deities. Daoism had a large and diverse pantheon, and various spiritual or deified beings might serve as transmitters of sacred scriptures in addition to supreme deities. For instance, the Shangqing scriptures (incorporated into the Three Caverns canon drawn upon by Chongxuan theorists) were said to have been revealed to a medium in his dreams by a series of divine beings known as the Perfected (zhenren 真人).

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 由至高无上的神启示：

— 否

Notes: Because Laozi plays a direct and active role in creating and disseminating the Daodejing (and other deities, such as the Heavenly Worthy of Primordial Commencement, play similar roles for other scriptures), it would be an understatement to say that such works are "inspired" by a high god as that would suggest a human author working from divine inspiration, rather than a divine author creating or revealing a text.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 由其他超自然生灵启示：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 来源于神或半神半人：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 来源于凡人：

— 是

Notes: The Daodejing is an ambiguous case of this because it was written and bestowed upon the gatekeeper, Yin Xi 尹喜, by Laozi prior to the latter's departure from the Zhou domain. Depending on one's perspective and context, Laozi could be considered a mortal human, a divine being, or a high god manifestation of the Dao itself (worshiped as Taishang Laojun 太上老君 from the Han dynasty onward).

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 这一经典是否是可以改变：

— 否

Notes: While the scriptures, such as the Daode jing as well as other Daoist scriptures, must have been altered to a certain extent over time because there are multiple versions, Daoist scriptures in early medieval China were nevertheless considered divine and therefore the greatest care had to be taken not to compromise their purity – and this refers to the text as words and script as well as to the text as material object. There are, for example, have stories and anecdotes of terrible repercussions, often in the form of sickness, for “mistreating” or neglecting scriptures,

and there are also Daoist scriptures which admonish Daoist priests to be careful when copying them. (See for example Bumbacher 2012, Assandri 2010, 392).

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 是否存在诠释经典的正式机构（比如被宗教团体或者政治领袖所授权的机构）：
— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 可以抛开这些机构来诠释经典吗：
— 是

Notes: It is worth noting that, while sacred scriptures like the Benji jing were read and interpreted only by Daoists, the Daode jing was read and interpreted by a wide variety of figures (including Buddhists, Daoists, and Confucians) and was subject to many different understandings over time and in different contexts.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 只有被正式批准的人员才可以诠释经典：
— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 是否存在一个专门被训练从事经典传布的特定群体：
— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 是否存在一部结集的典籍经藏：
— 是

Notes: This applies only to the larger codifications of the "Daoist Canon" (daozeang 道藏). Chongxuan texts were incorporated into the main Daoist corpus and were not codified into a separate canon.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

是否存在纪念性的宗教建筑物：

一是

Notes: The institutional form of Daoism was the "temple or "abbey" (guan 觀) in which lived Daoist priests and monastics, including representatives of Chongxuan. In Chang'an, prominent temples included the Haotianguan 豪天觀, Dongmingguan 東明觀, and Xihuaguan 西華觀.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 在一般的定居地，所有宗教纪念性质建筑、纪念物面积所占百分比是多少：

— 未知领域

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 最大的单体宗教纪念物、建筑的面积，以平方米计

— 未知领域

Notes: Although it is difficult to tie Chongxuan representatives to specific temples, and little is known about Daoist structures in the early medieval period, Thomas Thilo has identified the size of the largest Daoist temple in the capital during the Tang dynasty. According to Thilo, this temple (the Haotianguan 豪天觀, "Abbey of Great Heaven"), which was founded in 656 CE, filled the entire quarter in which it was built and was thus 530x562 meters, or 30 ha. Other temples in which Chongxuan Daoists were known to have lived, such as the Dongmingguan 東明觀 (Abbey of Eastern Brightness) and Xihuaguan 西華觀 (Abbey of Western Flourishing), were smaller in size, occupying approximately one quarter or less of the quarter in which they were located. For more, see Thilo 2006, 343.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 最大的单体宗教纪念物、建筑的高度，以米计

— 未知领域

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 一般纪念物、建筑的尺寸，平方米

— 未知领域

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 一般纪念建筑、纪念物的高度，米

— 未知领域

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

在最大的定居地，所有宗教纪念物、纪念建筑总体面积所占区域百分比是多少？

— 未知领域

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

有不同种类的宗教纪念性建筑物吗？

— 我不知道

Notes: According to Li Yangzheng, Daoist architecture in the Tang dynasty did have multiple types, such as smaller temples designed as “guan 觀,” which might include a look-out tower (inspired by the look-out tower of Yin Xi, the guardian of the pass who received the Daodejing from Laozi), and larger ensembles of buildings around a courtyard, which were built more like palaces and termed “gong 宮” due to the relationship between the Tang royal house and Laozi (Li 1993, 471-491). However, the lack of extant evidence for Daoist structures in the Tang (the oldest surviving Daoist temple being the Guangrenmiao 廣仁廟, also called Wulong miao 五龍廟, in Shanxi dated to 831) means that this is uncertain and more research is required.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

是否存在表征标志

— 是

Notes: Chongxuan teachings developed within the institutional context of Daoist monasteries in the capitals of major polities such as the Tang dynasty. Although Chongxuan itself was not explicitly concerned with iconography, it is virtually certain that, beginning in the Northern Wei, Daoist monasteries began to feature iconography. For more detailed discussions, see Liu 2001, Kohn 2004, 97-102, and Karetzky 2017.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

表征在哪里显示【多选】

— 在家里

— 在一些公共场所

Notes: As noted in the above comment, Chongxuan was a teaching within Daoism and so the typical characteristics of Daoist iconography during the Tang would apply to Chongxuan as well. At the very least, Daoist iconography would have been present in temples, on altars, caves, and votive stele (Karetzky 2017). As pointed out by Lennart Gesterkamp (2011, 12-14), there are also descriptions of paintings that would have adorned Daoist ritual spaces (though, sadly, the paintings themselves have not survived). It is also important to note that, while scholars assume that iconography was present “at home,” based in part on present-day practices, scholars do not know this for certain.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 宗教团体的表征标志有明显特色吗

— 是

Notes: For a helpful discussion of Daoist iconography in the Tang, readers are encouraged to consult Karetzky 2017.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 眼睛（是否写实）

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 超自然的存在(兽形)

— 是

Notes: Descriptions of paintings that would have adorned Daoist ritual spaces around 500 CE, mention the presence of dragons and phoenixes in the paintings (Gesterkamp 2011, 14).

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 超自然的存在(地貌外形)

— 是

Notes: Descriptions of paintings that would have adorned Daoist ritual spaces around 500 CE, mention the presence of sacred Daoist landscapes such as Mount Kunlun (a residence of immortals) and Jade Mountain (located in the Daoist heavens). Although these landscapes are not "beings" per se, they are important sacred and "supernatural" geomorphic entities (Gesterkamp 2011, 14).

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 超自然的存在(人形)

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 超自然的存在(抽象的象征符号)

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 对来世的描绘

— 是

Notes: Descriptions of paintings that would have adorned Daoist ritual spaces around 500 CE, mention the presence of sacred Daoist landscapes such as Jade Mountain, which is located in the Daoist heavens (Gesterkamp 2011, 14).

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 教义方面（比如，十字架、三位一体、密特拉教符号）

— 我不知道

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 人类

— 我不知道

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 表征有其它特色：

— 我不知道

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

是否有专门的地点用于神圣行活动或者被认为是神圣的：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 神圣场地是否适应环境特点：

“环境特点”指的是风景、山水、罗盘方位等等的特征。

— 否

Notes: Although Chongxuan (as part of the larger Daoist tradition) did have sacred sites, these tended to be oriented toward hagiographical traditions, rather than environmental features.

For instance, Louguan 樓觀 (Lou Abbey) was located on the site where Laozi was believed to have written the Daode jing. The important Daoist topos of cavern-heavens, which designate special places in locations like mountains, does not seem to play a major role in Chongxuan thought, even though it is of prominent importance in the medieval Daoist traditions of the south.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

有朝圣活动吗：

— 我不知道

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

信仰

埋葬和来世

是否存在精神-肉体的区分

只有当人格（或意识）随肉体死亡而消亡时回答“否”。回答是并不一定意味着存在笛卡尔精神/肉体二元论，而只意味着人格（或意识）的一些要素在肉体死后尚存。

— 是

Notes: As mentioned in chapters 63, 64 and 72,73,74 of Cheng Xuanying's commentary to the Daode jing, Chongxuan Daoism (and Daoism more generally) incorporated the concept of karmic rebirth as well as visions of the afterlife that were influenced by Buddhist concepts such as the Pure Land (particularly in the Benji jing). As a result, there is a sense that some type of personhood survives the body's demise.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 精神 – 心灵被认为具有异乎其它身体部位的能力或特质

— 是

Notes: Insofar as personhood can survive the death of the body, it may be considered as possessing qualitatively different powers or properties from the body. Furthermore, Chongxuan thinkers proposed that the “mind” (xin 心), seat of cognition and emotion, is the organ that is able to realize Dao as a person's true nature, also called Dao-nature, provided it is perfectly still.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 精神 – 心灵被认为是非物质的，在本体论上不同于身体

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 其它心灵-身体关系：

一是: Qi-based monism

Notes: Daoism posits a qi-based cosmology in which both spirit and body are composed of the same substance, qi, albeit of varying degrees of refinement. As a consequence, spirit and body are not only not ontologically distinct from one another, but the qi of the body can also be refined in order to achieve "bodily" immortality (in which the distinction of body and spirit blurs even further).

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

对来世的信仰：

一是

Notes: Scriptures such as the Benji jing show some co-option of Buddhist concepts, such as that of the Pure Land, and Cheng Xuanying discusses the afterlife in detail in his commentary to the Daode jing (chapters 63, 64, 72-74, see Assandri 2021). From these mentions, it is clear that Chongxuan, and Daoism more generally, incorporated notions of reincarnation/rebirth.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 该宗教团体对来世的空间位置有具体描述吗

一是

Notes: The Daoist conception of the afterlife includes both the bureaucratic Heavens above, where dwell those who have successfully achieved immortality, and the bureaucratic underworld below wherein underworld officials mete out punishment and retribution based on karma (Assandri 2009, 153; 164; 209).

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 来世在这个世界之外的特定领域空间：

一是

Notes: The presence of heavens above and hells below suggests that the afterlife lies beyond the bounds of the mortal world. It is important to note, however, that the borders of these realms are very porous, especially those that separate the human world from the underworld (see Bokenkamp 2007 for an exhaustive discussion).

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 来世被模糊定义为“上面”的空间：

— 是

Notes: Immortals dwell in the Heavens above.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 来世被模糊定义为“下面”的空间：

— 是

Notes: Those who have not cultivated themselves travel to the bureaucratic underworld after death where they are judged by underworld officials. Specific underworld locations include Fengdu 豐都, Jiuyou 九幽, Luofeng 羅酆, and Quanqu 泉曲 - these are mentioned in chapters 72-74 of Cheng Xuanying's commentary to the Daodejing.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 来世被模糊定义为某个平行空间：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 来世在“其他”空间：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

在这个世界上的转世

— 是

Notes: Reincarnation in this world, the world of the humans, is possible and preferable to reincarnation in the underworld or hells or as an animal. Chongxuan thinkers have incorporated Buddhist concepts of reincarnation here, in particular the concept of six gatis (liudao 六道) as six different destinations of rebirth. Rebirth in the human world is one of them. For an example see Cheng Xuanying's commentary to the Daode jing, chapter 58 (Assandri 2021, 281-282).

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 以人形转世：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 以动物/植物的形态转世：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 以非生物的形式转世：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 以非个体的形式转世（比如集体重生、部落、家族等等）：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 和超越此生的因果机制有联系（比如，业力）：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 这个世界中的其他形式的转世

— 是: The six paths of rebirth include being reborn as a hungry ghost. Unlike demons or gods (which a person can also be reborn as), hungry ghosts are present in the human world.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

对信众的遗体有特别处置吗：

— 未知领域

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

埋葬过程中或者墓穴中是否存在一起殉葬现象

— 未知领域

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

是否存在陪葬品：

— 我不知道

Notes: Grave goods were a common feature of pre-modern Chinese burials and the Tang dynasty made use of mingqi 明器 burial figurines just like preceding periods. However, it is unclear if Daoists in general, and Chongxuan adherents in particular, also followed this practice.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

有正式的葬礼吗：

— 我不知道

Notes: Burials in China were generally formal, particularly for important figures, and this is documented also for Buddhist clerics as well. Although it seems likely that Daoists followed these customs as well, I am not aware of documentation corroborating that they did so.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

超自然存在

有超自然存在吗：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

有一个至上之神存在

— 是

Notes: One of Chongxuan's most important innovations was to devise a means of combining the different high gods of different branches of Daoism, particularly Laozi (associated with the Celestial Masters lineage) and the Heavenly Worthy of Primordial Commencement (associated with the southern tradition of the Three Caverns). The means by which this was accomplished was Cheng Xuanying's use of the concept of the two bodies of the sage and the logic of the tetra lemma. The "two bodies" concept is derived from the Buddhist trikaya concept (the idea that the Buddha has three kinds of bodies or manifestations, an eternal, dharma body, a bliss body which appears in paradise, and a response body. The historical Buddha was the response body manifestation of the eternal dharma body). The Daoist "two bodies" concept takes the dharma body as the "truth body" (zhenshen 真身), which it contrasts to the "response body" (yingshen 应身). By submitting this concept to the logic of the tetra lemma on the model of the two-fold truth, Cheng Xuanying was able to argue in a logically and theologically rigorous way for the complete interpenetration of the Dao as the ultimate, yet empty, metaphysical unity of all things (understood as the truth body) and deities such as the Heavenly Worthy of Primordial Commencement or Laozi, who could also be conceptualized as a human sage (the response body). An important consequence of this interpenetration between Dao and Laozi was that the Dao came to be defined by anthropomorphic characteristics such as wisdom and compassion and was thus thought to actively assist in the salvation of all things because of its infinite

compassion. For a full discussion see Assandri 2009, 152-192.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 至上之神是人形：

— 是

Notes: As mentioned above, the logical interpenetration of Laozi and the Dao endowed the latter with anthropomorphic characteristics such as wisdom and compassion (Assandri 2009, 189-191). However, it was at the same time also conceived as ineffable absolute, which defied any specific characteristic.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 至上之神是天神

— 是

Notes: The Dao encompasses all of existence but many of its divine manifestations are explicitly associated with Daoist heavens, such as the Heavenly Worthy of Primordial Commencement. Insofar as these heavens are informed by sky imagery, such deities may be considered "sky deities" (Assandri 2009, 162-163).

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 至上之神是地府的神灵（地底世界的）：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 至上之神与君主不分（王=至高的神）

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 君主被视作至上之神的表现和化身：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 至上之神和精英阶层有亲属关系

—是

Notes: During the Tang dynasty, the imperial clan claimed to be descendants of Laozi, based on their family name of Li 李 (traditionally thought of as Laozi's family name as well). By claiming that the Dao and Laozi were logically interpenetrating, Chongxuan theorists thus provided strong support for the authority of the imperial house.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 至上之神和精英有其它类型的效忠关系

—否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 至高之神是不可质疑的善

—是

Notes: This question is difficult to answer decisively. Although the Chongxuan conception of Laozi as the supreme god seems to be unquestionably good, Dao itself (which is synonymous and interpenetrating with Laozi) is frequently positioned beyond good and bad in different Daoist texts. This is an instance of the difficulty implied in having an abstract absolute (Dao) beyond any distinctions, and its identification with a concretely described deity. This tension has haunted Daoists throughout history, especially in the debates with Buddhists which were held at the courts of the early Tang emperors, and which are recorded in Ji gujin Fo Dao lunheng 集古今佛道论衡 (T 2104).

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 至上之神的其它特征：

—是: Two bodies of the sage, compassion.

Notes: In addition to the logical interpenetration of Dao and Laozi, Dao is understood as compassionate in nature, which leads it to actively work toward the salvation of all things. This latter point is strongly emphasized within Chongxuan teachings (Assandri 2009, 162-163).

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 至上之神具有关于这个世界的知识：

—是

Notes: Chapter four of Daoxuan's Ji gujin Fo Dao lunheng 集古今佛道论衡 (T 2104) records an interesting debate regarding the question of Dao and its knowledge of the world that was held in 658 at the court of emperor Gaozong between the Buddhist Huili (615-ca. 675) and an important representative of Chongxuan thought, the Daoist Li

Rong (discussed in Assandri 2015).

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 至上之神只对特定的领域的人类事务有所认知：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 至上之神的知识限于采样地区的（一个或多个）特定区域：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 至上之神的知识在采样地区没有限制：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 至上之神的知识对采样地区以外没有限制：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 不论你（在公共场所）置身何处，至上之神都可以看到你

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 不论你身处何处，至上之神都可以看到你（即便在黑暗中、在家里）：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 至上之神可以看穿你的心/脑（隐秘的动机）：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 至上之神知道你的基本特征个性（个人本质）：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 至上之神知道你将来的人生际遇／你将来会做什么（预测的能力）：

— 是

Notes: Generally, the supreme high god is said to be omniscient, however, it seems that the knowledge of others is emphasized rather with regard to previous lives than with regard to the future. See for example Cheng Xuanying's commentary to the Daode jing, chapter 33, which states that the supreme god (or Laozi) has knowledge of the incarnations and lives of all people (cf. Assandri 2021, 176).

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 至上之神关于这个世界有其他知识：

— 是: The Dao and esoteric teachings

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 至上之神对这个世界能够有意施发因果效力：

— 是

Notes: Although the Dao is understood as supremely powerful, this is not conceptualized in terms of rewards and punishments. Karmically-derived punishments are meted out by underworld officials, while the Dao is motivated by compassion and its salvific power can override the logic and mechanisms of karma.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 至上之神能奖赏

— 否

Notes: Although the Dao is understood as supremely powerful, this is not conceptualized in terms of rewards and punishments. Karmically-derived punishments are meted out by underworld officials, while the Dao is motivated by compassion and its salvific power can override the logic and mechanisms of karma.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 至上之神能惩罚：

— 否

Notes: Although the Dao is understood as supremely powerful, this is not conceptualized in terms of rewards and punishments. Karmically-derived punishments are meted out by underworld officials, while the Dao is motivated by compassion and its salvific power can override the logic and mechanisms of karma.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

↳ 至上之神对这个世界上可以施发间接的因果效力：

— 是

Notes: Dao is considered the origin of all things and, thus, the ultimate grounding for all actions in the cosmos. This can be interpreted as a kind of indirect efficacy. However, it is important to note that the process of the cosmos unfolding from the Dao is never discussed as a process of creation (with, for example, Laozi acting as a creator god). Instead, it is presented more abstractly and mechanistically.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 至上之神展现其积极的情感：

— 是

Notes: The only positive emotion that the Dao can be said to possess is compassion (for which, see note above). All other emotions were considered biased and flawed and so were not present.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 至上之神展现其负面的情感：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 至上之神有饥饿感：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 除了至高之神以外，允许崇拜其他超自然存在吗：

—是

Notes: Daoism had a complex development during the Six Dynasties period (220-581 CE), with different groups of people revering different deities, but all claiming to be connected to Dao. Chongxuan is part of a strand of Daoism which made great efforts to integrate the different groups with their texts and deities. The process of integration was achieved rather by means of hierarchical sub-ordinations, so multiple deities remained important and are revered in Daoism (Assandri 2009, 152ff)

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 至上之神具备/展现出其他一些特征：

—是: The supreme god Laozi is perceived as a manifestation of Dao. Dao is ultimate nonbeing, and the origin and rule of all being. Chongxuan thinkers combined the concept of two bodies of the sage (an abstract truth body and a concrete response body; a concept, which had been adapted from the Buddhist Trikaya concept) and an ancient concept of Three Ones, or three in one (the Chinese term sanyi 三一—allows both interpretations) to achieve a logically coherent integration of the abstract Dao and the concrete manifestation as the deity Lord Lao or Laozi. The same logical operation that built on dialectic combinations of one and three allowed them further to integrate Dao and Laozi with other deities. (See Assandri 2009, 173-191).

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 至上之神和生灵有沟通：

—是

Notes: In general, Daoism is a religion heavily based on divine revelations that can take a variety of forms. Perhaps the most famous example is Laozi's revelation to Zhang Daoling 张道陵 (2nd century CE) (which began the lineage of the Celestial Masters). Another example is the theophany of one Ji Shanxing 吉善行 (Mr. Good Omen Good Conduct), later revealed to be Laozi in a further visitation in 620 CE (Assandri 2009, 23-24). Kou Qianzhi 寇谦之 (365?-448) also claimed that Laozi had appeared to him during his efforts to establish a state Daoism based on the Celestial Masters lineage. In Southern denominations of Daoism, the supreme god (the Heavenly Worthy of Primordial Commencement) is so far distant from humanity that it does not communicate and revelations are typically given by lesser deities. Given that Chongxuan developed within Tang Daoism that incorporated all of these lineages, we can find a variety of perspectives, including that the supreme high god does communicate.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 在清醒状态下的日常生活中：

—是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 在睡梦中：

—是

Notes: As mentioned above, revelations in Daoism can take a variety of forms. For instance, the Shangqing revelations (which were, albeit, by lesser deities) took place entirely within dreams.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 在被附体催眠状态中：

—否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 通过占卜行为：

—我不知道

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 只通过宗教专业人员：

—否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 只通过君主：

—否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 其他与生灵的交流方式：

—是: Transmission of divinely-revealed teachings

Notes: As narrated in the Benji jing, the supreme god can at times hand down sacred scriptures to lesser deities who, in turn, transmit those teachings to chosen mortals (Assandri 2009, 57-70).

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 过去人的灵魂是存在的：

— 是

Notes: The subsequent questions under this question are answered as "Field doesn't know" because Chongxuan theorists do not discuss previously human spirits in any detail. It is clear that such spirits were thought to exist, that they traveled to the underworld bureaucracy of the afterlife, and that they were in need of salvation, but the details of their existence are not described in Chongxuan texts.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 人类灵魂可以被看到

— 我不知道

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 人类灵魂可以用身体感触到：

— 未知领域

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 过去人的灵魂对这个世界有所认知：

— 未知领域

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 人类灵魂至上对这个世界能够有意施发因果效力：

— 未知领域

Notes: While we do not know how representatives of Chongxuan xue thought about human spirits precisely, it is important to note that in a more general way, the spirits of deceased human beings were believed to have the potential of bringing sickness and calamities over the living, especially if they were not treated properly (see Peter Nickerson's translation of the great Petition for Sepulchral Plaints in Bokenkamp 1997, 230ff). The same issue is alluded to in Daode jing chapter 60, and Cheng Xuanying mentions in his commentary that ghosts (that is spirits of deceased human beings) from the underworld can give blessings or do harm to the human beings. (Assandri 2021, 291).

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 人类灵魂对这个世界有间接因果效应：

— 未知领域

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 人类灵魂对人生有记忆：

— 未知领域

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 人类灵魂展现出积极的情感：

— 未知领域

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 人类灵魂展现出负面的情感：

— 未知领域

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 人类灵魂有饥饿感：

— 未知领域

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 人类灵魂有/展现出一些其他特征：

— 未知领域

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 人类灵魂和生灵沟通：

— 未知领域

Notes: We do not know if Chongxuan thinkers believed that human spirits would communicate with the living, because the specific Chongxuan texts don't seem to talk about it. However, it should be noted that in general, Daoists did believe in

communication between the spirits and the living. See Bokenkamp 2007, 39-50 and 98-101.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 有非人类的超自然存在：

— 是

Notes: Chongxuan Daoism places comparatively less emphasis on supernatural beings than other strands of Daoism, focusing instead on the interpenetration of apparently separate entities such as deities, the Dao, and adepts who obtain it. However, insofar as Chongxuan partakes of larger syntheses in Daoism, including that of the Lingbao and Shangqing teachings, it can be said to possess a number of supernatural beings, including primordial deities such as The Heavenly Worthy of Primordial Commencement, lesser deities and celestial transcendents (former humans who have achieved immortality through self-cultivation), and bodily deities who dwell within humans and play a key role in self-cultivation and the attainment of immortality (Assandri 2009, 139; 152-172; 173-191). Chongxuan scriptures, such as the Benji jing, thus feature a variety of supernatural beings in their accounts (Assandri 2009, 57-70).

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 这些超自然存在可以被看到：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 这些超自然存在可以用身体感触到：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 非人类的超自然存在对这个世界有认知：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 非人类的超自然存在的所知限于特定的领域人类事务：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 非人类的超自然存在的所知限于采样地区的（一个或多个）特定区域：
— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 非人类的超自然存在对采样地区内无所不知：
— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 非人类的超自然存在对采样地区以外无所不知：
— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 不论你（在公共场所）置身何处，非人类的超自然存都可以看到你：
— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 不论你置身何处非人类的超自然存在都可以看到你（比如在黑暗中和家里）：
— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 非人类的超自然存在可以看穿你的心/脑中（隐秘的动机）：
— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 非人类的超自然存在知道你的基本特征个性（个人本质）：
— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 非人类的超自然存在知道你将来的人生际遇/你将会做什么（预测未来的能

力) :

— 我不知道

Notes: This is difficult to answer for supernatural beings in general, as they are not a focus of Chongxuan theorizing. However, the Chongxuan model of the sage is one who returns to the Dao, which is considered completely interpenetrating with apparently separate deities, and then chooses to return to the world and save others out of compassion (much like a Buddhist Bodhisattva). Because the sage returns to, and thus becomes one with, the Dao, they seem to possess something like omniscience. Chongxuan thinkers distinguish between expedient and real wisdom (for example in chapters 3 and 31 of Cheng Xuanying's commentary to the Daode jing), where real wisdom is the wisdom related to obtaining Dao, while expedient wisdom is worldly wisdom or knowledge of the things of the world. Chongxuan writings focus more on the process of returning to the Dao and the subsequent work of saving all other beings, which relates to "real wisdom," than they do on the expedient wisdom concerning worldly things. (Assandri 2009, 173-191).

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 非人类的超自然存在对这个世界有其他的认知 :

—是: Knowledge of heavens and esoteric teachings

Notes: Supernatural beings, most of whom reside in the heavens or the underworld, naturally possess knowledge of the world that exceeds, and is different from, that possessed by humans. At the same time, they may be the first recipients of divinely revealed teachings that are then transmitted to humans, as, for example, in the Benji jing (Assandri 2009, 57-71).

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 非人类的超自然存在对这个世界可以有意施发因果效应 :

—是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 这些超自然存在可以奖赏 :

—是

Notes: An important general feature of Daoism is the belief that scriptures themselves have supernatural powers and can thus offer protection from harm. These powers come from the scriptures themselves as well as from supernatural beings, Jade Maidens and Jade Lads, who accompany the scriptures and watch over the scriptures and their owners. There are suggestions that this idea of supernatural protection applied to Chongxuan scriptures such as the Benji jing and Huming jing (Assandri 2009, 61-62). This belief can be interpreted as an idea of reward because it means that if one

receives a scripture, which requires devotion to Daoist ideas, one can obtain a measure of supernatural protection in their lifetime.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 这些超自然存在可以惩罚：

— 是

Notes: Punishments in the afterlife are typically thought to be carried out by underworld officials, who are considered relatively minor deities. Higher deities such as Laozi and the Heavenly Worthy of Primordial Commencement are, presumably, capable of punishment due to their immense power, but they are only described as saving others because of their compassionate natures.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 这些超自然存在对这个世界有间接的因果效应：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 这些超自然存在展现出积极的情感：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 这些超自然存在展现出负面的情感：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 这些超自然存在有饥饿感：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 这些超自然存在有/展现出一些其他特征：

— 是: Manifestations/emanations of the Dao

Notes: Because Chongxuan theorists defend the idea that the Dao is completely

interpenetrating with apparently separate deities and that it is the source of the cosmos, all deities may be thought of as emanations or manifestations of the Dao. As a result, deities are also associated with salvation in different ways. For example, body deities are associated with salvation through the role they play in the self-cultivation techniques needed to return oneself to the Dao while the Dao itself, as well as other high deities such as Laozi and the Heavenly Worthy of Primordial Commencement, are thought to actively work for the salvation of all beings.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 有半人半神的存在：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 宗教团体具有多种超自然存在：

— 是

Notes: Chongxuan Daoism places comparatively little emphasis on supernatural beings than other strands of Daoism, focusing instead on the interpenetration of apparently separate entities such as deities, the Dao, and adepts who obtain it. However, insofar as Chongxuan partakes of larger syntheses in Daoism, including that of the Lingbao and Shangqing teachings, it can be said to possess a number of supernatural beings, including primordial deities such as The Heavenly Worthy of Primordial Commencement, lesser deities and celestial transcendents (former humans who have achieved immortality through self-cultivation), and bodily deities who dwell within humans and play a key role in self-cultivation and the attainment of immortality (Assandri 2009, 139; 152-172; 173-191). Chongxuan scriptures, such as the Benji jing, thus feature a variety of supernatural beings in their accounts (Assandri 2009, 57-70).

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 以基于家庭模式的亲属关系编排：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 按照高下阶层编排：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 各自的权力是限于所属领域的：

一是

Notes: While Chongxuan authors do not seem to refer much to beings whose power is limited to specific domains, we should note that Daoism in general does know supernatural beings whose power is limited to specific domains. One example of beings whose power is limited to a specific domain could be the underworld authorities mentioned in chapter 74 of Cheng Xuanying's Expository Commentary to the Daode jing (cf. Assandri 2021, 341-343).

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

万神庙的其他组织方式：

一是: Cosmic Bureaucracy

Notes: In Daoism, the gods, immortals, spirits, and officials of the Heavens and the underworld are organized into elaborate hierarchies, and partake of hierarchical bureaucracies.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

超自然监督

是否存在超自然的监视：

“超自然监视”是指超自然存在监视人类的行为以及或者思想，特别是涉及到社会准则或潜在性违规的情况。

一是

Notes: Although Chongxuan teachings indicate the existences of powerful deities, including the supreme entity of the Dao and the minor underworld deities who mete out punishments in the afterlife, they generally do not emphasize a monitoring aspect of these figures. Instead, they focus on the compassionate nature of Dao and its intention to actively save all entities due to that compassion (Assandri 2009, 104). With the co-opting of the theory of karmic retribution, Chongxuan thinkers nevertheless did assume that there were supernatural beings, residing in the underworld, who monitored the beings and cast a “net of justice”, punishing all misbehavior, as Cheng Xuanying explains in detail in chapter 74 of his Commentary to the Daode jing.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

有针对遵守亲社会规范的超自然监视：

亲社会规范是指增加族群中成员协作的规范，包括明显的“道德”或“伦理”规范，也延伸至关于履行合约与誓言，提供热情款待，在紧急情况下互相帮助等等。

一是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 超自然存在在意禁忌：

— 我不知道

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 超自然存在关切教友之间的杀害：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 超自然存在关切其他宗教的信徒的谋杀：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 超自然存在关切其它政权成员的谋杀：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 超自然存在关注性行为：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 通奸：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 乱伦：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 其他性行为：

—是: Celibacy of religious professionals and licentiousness in general

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 超自然存在在意撒谎行为：

—是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 超自然存在在意誓言的执行：

—是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 超自然存在在意懒惰：

—否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 超自然存在在意巫术：

—是

Notes: Here, "sorcery" is understood as those arts related to the practices of popular religion that focused on blood propitiation, as opposed to the worship of Daoist deities.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 超自然存在在意非致命的打斗：

—是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 超自然存在注意规避风险：

—否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 超自然存在在意对长者的不敬：

一是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 超自然存在在乎说长道短的行为：

一否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 超自然存在在意财产犯罪：

一是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 超自然存在在乎对仪礼的正确奉守：

一是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 超自然存在在乎仪式的演绎：

一是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 超自然存在在意度化无宗教信仰者：

一是

Notes: Here, "conversion" is understood as synonymous with cultivating Daoist practices in order to return to the Dao as a soteriological strategy.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 超自然存在在意经济上的公平：

一是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 超自然存在在意个人卫生：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 超自然存在在意其他事物：

— 是: Returning to the Dao

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

超自然存在施加惩罚吗：

— 是

Notes: Although Chongxuan teachings indicate the existences of powerful deities, including the supreme entity of the Dao and the minor underworld deities who mete out punishments in the afterlife, they generally do not emphasize a monitoring aspect of these figures. Instead, they focus on the compassionate nature of Dao and its intention to actively save all entities due to that compassion (Assandri 2009, 104). With the co-opting of the theory of karmic retribution, Chongxuan thinkers nevertheless did assume that there were supernatural beings, residing in the underworld, who monitored the beings and cast a “net of justice”, punishing all misbehavior, as Cheng Xuanying explains in detail in chapter 74 of his Commentary to the Daode jing.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 超自然惩罚的来源或是动因是已知的吗：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 只由至上之神完成

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 由许多超自然存在完成：

— 是

Notes: Punishments in the afterlife are meted out by underworld officials, not the Dao.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 由客观的因果定律来完成：

— 是

Notes: Although the underworld officials are the agents of punishment, the ultimate cause of the punishments is thought to be karma.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 由其他实体或其他方式完成【请注明】：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 超自然惩罚的存在原因是已知的吗：

— 是

Notes: In the interpretation of Chongxuan thinkers like Cheng Xuanying, the reason for supernatural punishments is based on accumulated karma.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 为了实现宗教的仪式-崇拜的信奉：

— 是

Notes: Insofar as immoral or unethical behaviour (which produces bad karma) can include a lack of ritual-devotional adherence.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 为了强制实施团体准则：

— 是

Notes: Insofar as immoral or unethical behaviour (which produces bad karma) can include the violation of Daoist norms.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 为了阻止自私自利：

— 是

Notes: Insofar as immoral or unethical behaviour (which produces bad karma) involves selfishness.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 随机：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 其它【请注明】

— 是

Notes: Karma

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 超自然惩罚在来世施行：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 宗教团体非常强调来世的超自然惩罚：

— 否

Notes: Although Chongxuan thinkers acknowledged the existence of underworld officials and punishments in the afterlife, their attention was focused on the salvific and compassionate nature of the Dao, as well as how to become an equally compassionate saviour sage.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 来世的惩罚包括轻微的感觉不悦：

— 是

Notes: While there are descriptions of Daoist hells at this time, Chongxuan thinkers did not focus on them and their writings contain relatively few allusions to them. For possible exceptions in the writings of Cheng Xuanying, see the notes below.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 来世的惩罚包括极度的感觉的不悦：

— 是

Notes: While there are descriptions of Daoist hells at this time, Chongxuan thinkers did

not focus on them and their writings contain relatively few allusions to them. For possible exceptions in the writings of Cheng Xuanying, see the notes below.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 来世的惩罚包括转世成为低等生命形式：

— 是

Notes: Chongxuan Daoists appear to have co-opted the theory of the six states of rebirth from Buddhism, where one can be reborn in hell, as a hungry ghost, a demon, an animal, human being, or heavenly deity. The term "six paths" (liudao 六道), which implies this idea, appears in Chapter 50 of Cheng Xuanying's commentary to the Daodejing. Furthermore, Cheng Xuanying also mentions, in chapter 30 of the commentary for example, the "three unfavorable destinations" (santu 三塗), which could be either the Buddhist states of hell, hungry ghosts and animals, or else the Daoist hells of fire, blood, and swords (all of which were thought to be present in the underworld and to involve physical displeasure).

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 来世的惩罚包括转世到低级领域：

— 是

Notes: Chongxuan Daoists appear to have co-opted the theory of the six states of rebirth from Buddhism, where one can be reborn in hell, as a hungry ghost, a demon, an animal, human being, or heavenly deity. The term "six paths" (liudao 六道), which implies this idea, appears in Chapter 50 of Cheng Xuanying's commentary to the Daodejing. Furthermore, Cheng Xuanying also mentions, in chapter 30 of the commentary for example, the "three unfavorable destinations" (santu 三塗), which could be either the Buddhist states of hell, hungry ghosts and animals, or else the Daoist hells of fire, blood, and swords (all of which were thought to be present in the underworld and to involve physical displeasure).

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 其它【请注明】

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 超自然惩罚在今世施行：

— 否

Notes: Although it may be possible in Daoist belief for individual moral failings to be linked to diseases and bad luck (which might then be considered "supernatural punishments"), this idea

is generally not emphasized by Chongxuan thinkers, who seem to largely limit supernatural punishments to the afterlife.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

超自然存在赐予奖赏吗：

—是

Notes: Although the Dao is understood as supremely powerful, this is not conceptualized in terms of rewards and punishments. Instead, the Dao is motivated by compassion to offer salvation to all beings. However, an important general feature of Daoism is the belief that scriptures themselves have supernatural powers and can thus offer protection from harm. These powers come from the scriptures themselves as well as from supernatural beings, Jade Maidens and Jade Lads, who accompany the scriptures and watch over the scriptures and their owners. There are suggestions that this idea of supernatural protection applied to Chongxuan scriptures such as the Benji jing and Huming jing (Assandri 2009, 61-62). This belief can be interpreted as an idea of reward because it means that if one receives a scripture, which requires devotion to Daoist ideas, one can obtain a measure of supernatural protection in their lifetime.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 超自然奖赏的来源/目的是已知的吗：

—是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 只由至高的神完成：

—否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 由许多超自然存在完成：

—是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 由客观的因果定律完成：

—是

Notes: Karma

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 为了实现宗教的仪式-崇拜的信奉：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 为了推行团体规范：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 为了阻止自私自利：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 随机：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 在来世赐予超自然奖赏：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 宗教团体非常强调来世的超自然奖赏：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 来世的奖赏包括轻微的感官愉悦：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 来世的奖赏包括极度的感官愉悦：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 来世的奖赏包括永恒的幸福：

— 否

Notes: Chapter 5 of the Benji jing includes depictions of immortals “of lower ranks” that do not seem to experience eternal happiness (Assandri 2009, 209). More importantly, chapter 6 of the Benji jing co-opts the concept of the Pure Land, which, in Buddhism, is a heavenly paradise that offers happiness for a long time, but not forever. This is because the ultimate goal in Buddhism is to realize Nirvana, a task made easier by the opportunity to be happy and meditate in the Pure Land for a certain period of time after one’s death. Similarly, in Chongxuan Daoism, the prospect of a joyful existence in paradise is not intended as ultimate or final solution and is, thus, not conceptualized as “eternal.” Instead, the ultimate aim of Chongxuan practice is to unite with or obtain the Dao and thereby overcome the dichotomy of life and death, meaning that one can move between the two states of being and nonbeing at will – motivated by compassion. Therefore, while Chongxuan (and Buddhist) conceptions of paradises and heavens may bear some resemblance to, for example, Christian conceptions of heaven, they are fundamentally different in seeing these postmortem spaces as temporary, not permanent, destinations.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 来世的奖赏包括转世为更高级生命形式：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 来世的奖赏包括投生到更高级的领域中：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 其它【请注明】

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 在今世赐予超自然奖赏：

一是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 宗教团体非常强调今世的超自然奖赏：

一是

Notes: For example, part of the appeal of texts like the Huming jing and Benji jing was their apotropaic qualities, meaning their ability to ward off misfortune and help bring about a state of Great Peace. The text themselves also emphasize rewards in this life and advertise their apotropaic qualities.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 今世的奖赏包括好运：

一是

Notes: This is a product of the apotropaic quality of scriptures.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 今世的奖赏包括政治上的成功或权力：

一是

Notes: Both the Huming jing and Benji jing emphasize that their apotropaic qualities can help one to gain political power (if the scriptures themselves are properly revered). As well, Cheng Xuanying's Commentary also seems to promise political power (though linked more to certain types of behavior, rather than supernatural intervention).

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 今世的奖赏包括在战斗的胜利：

一否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 今世的奖赏包括和平或社会稳定：

一是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 今世的奖赏包括好的收成或风调雨顺：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 今世的奖赏包括出行上一路顺风：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 今世的奖赏包括轻微的感觉愉悦：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 今世的奖赏包括极度的感觉愉悦：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 今世的奖赏包括更好的健康：

— 是

Notes: As mentioned elsewhere in this entry, an essential feature of Chongxuan (and Daoism in general) was the prospect of becoming immortal by returning to the Dao. Immortality in the Daoist tradition is closely connected to longevity and enhanced health. While Chongxuan thinkers developed a vision of immortality that overcomes the dichotomy of life and death, and thus theoretically also the dichotomy of health and sickness, the traditional theme of health and longevity was not lost to them at all, as for example Cheng Xuanying's commentary to chapters 5, 28, 42, 76 shows.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 今世的奖赏包括多子多孙：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 今世的奖赏包括子孙多福

— 是

Notes: Chapter 54 of Cheng Xuanying's Expository Commentary to the Daode jing proposes that a person can reach Dao and then transmit it to the following generations. He also might accumulate karmic blessings through good deeds, which can affect future generations. It is noteworthy that, as in the case of enhanced health, the rewards here are derived from practicing Daoism and obtaining the Dao. In other words, it is the adept himself who creates them. They are not meted out by supernatural beings.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

其它【请注明】

— 是

Notes: If properly revered, apotropaic scriptures confer protection on those who possess them.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

救世主/末世论

是否存在救世主信仰：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

存在某种末世论吗：

— 否

Notes: There are a number of eschatological currents in Daoism generally. For example, Highest Clarity (shangqing 上清) Daoism predicts that the world will end and be replaced by the rule of Great Peace (taiping 太平). However, eschatology was not a notable feature of the Chongxuan teaching (Assandri 2009, 156).

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

规范与道德现实

该宗教团体规定总体性的社会准则了吗：

— 是

Notes: In addition to occasionally advocating for wider social norms such as filial piety, Daoism had a highly developed and oft-repeated set of ethical virtues and values. These Daoist ethical virtues are compliance, contentedness (knowing to be content) femininity, generosity, humility, modesty, stillness

(as opposed to impetuosity), weakness and softness, and yieldingness. Chongxuan is also notable for its emphasis on compassionate salvation of all entities.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

该宗教团体存在传统和道德范畴的区分吗：

—是

Notes: Daoist virtues are frequently positioned in opposition to societal values. For example, while the wider society might value strength and exertion, Daoists value "weakness" and "yielding." All of these virtues are related to the most important Daoist and Chongxuan value, which is to return to the Dao and so achieve salvation. Because of the ultimate nature of the Dao, this normative injunction has greater authority and priority than any societal ethic.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 这种区别的性质是什么：

—存在且清晰

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 宗教团体对道德规范有专门规定吗：

—是

Notes: Daoist norms, articulated through the virtues discussed below, fulfilled two functions. On the one hand, they provided a way for human beings to function in society without harming themselves or others and ensuring society's smooth functioning. On the other hand, normative ways of behaving were thought to be imitations of how the Dao behaves and so help practitioners in their goal to "return to the Dao" and become immortal. Moreover, returning to the Dao was a way for the sage to help others achieve salvation by returning to the Dao as well. Sages thus operated according to the same ideas of universal compassion and salvation that characterized the Dao itself. It is, however, interesting to note that the Dao is characterized as being beyond good and evil and so those who return to it would be characterized in the same way, despite their compassionate efforts to achieve the salvation of all things.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 专门的道德规范和模糊的形而上学的观念模糊有不明显的联系：

—是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 专门的道德规范和模糊的形而上学的实体有明显的联系：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 专门的道德规范和客观的宇宙秩序的有联系（比如业力）：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 专门的道德规范以某种方式和人形的存在相联系：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 专门的道德规范和人形化的存在的命令有明显的联系：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 专门的道德规范和形而上的没有特别联系：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 道德规范适用于：

— 所有人（任何时代）

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

该宗教团体是否有提倡的核心重要美德：

— 是

Notes: Daoist ethical virtues are compliance, contentedness (knowing to be content) femininity, generosity, humility, modesty, stillness (as opposed to impetuosity), weakness and softness, and yieldingness. In addition, the goal of the returning to the Dao entails virtues such as tranquility/calm, compassion as the basis for salvation, and insight/understanding.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 诚实/忠信/正直 :

— 是

Notes: Xin 信 ("trustworthiness") plays a role in chapters 8, 38, and 63 of the Daodejing and is mentioned in Cheng Xuanying's commentary as an important virtue, if not quite as crucial as those listed above.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 勇敢（在战斗中） :

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 勇敢（一般意义上） :

— 否

Notes: Cheng Xuanying seems to reject "conventional" courage, which is to be equated with boldness and impetuosity, but he does characterize the sage as courageous when he enters the world to compassionately save the beings (chapter 67 of his Commentary to the Daode jing). This courage however, is a courage that selflessly aims at saving others, but never to prove something to the world.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 同情心/善解人意/善良/仁爱 :

— 是

Notes: While compassion (ci 慈) is endorsed very strongly by Chongxuan thinkers, we should note that benevolence (ren 仁) is ambivalent. It is at times equated with kindness and compassion, and therefore seen positive (see for example chapters 8 and 38 of Cheng Xuanying's Commentary to the Daode jing), and at other times equated with the Confucian cardinal virtue of benevolence (ren), which is rejected (especially based on Daode jing chapters 18 and 19). Daoists argued that benevolence was only needed because people did not heed the teachings of Dao, and furthermore they criticize that benevolence (ren) of the Confucians is partial and biased, while Daoist benevolence and compassion extend to all beings.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 仁慈/宽宥/包容 :

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 慷慨/博施济众：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 无私/无私奉献：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 仗义/正气：

— 是

Notes: While we can say that righteousness is endorsed by Chongxuan thinkers especially in a sense of following the religious precepts (see e.g. Cheng Xuanying's commentary to the Daode jing, ch. 38), we should note that the Confucian ideal of yi 義 (righteousness) is rejected in the Daode jing, and consequently also by Chongxuan thinkers in chapters 18 and 19 of the Daode jing as an inferior virtue, whose propagation only became necessary because the Great Dao was lost.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 仪式纯洁/奉守礼制/戒绝不纯洁之源：

— 是

Notes: This is not emphasized in Chongxuan texts but it was an important element of Daoist monastic rules and it is reasonable to assume that Chongxuan representatives followed these rules as well (cf. Kohn 2004, 122-123).

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 对人尊敬/讲礼貌：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 家庭内的恭顺/孝顺：

— 是

Notes: Although this question is answered "yes," the answer is complicated. Chongxuan Daoists were chujia 處家 Daoists, meaning they lived as celibate monastics outside of the family structure. However, given the importance of filial piety within the larger cultural context, Daoists adopted the Buddhist argument that monks were, in fact, more filial than those who remained at home and had children because their practices accumulated merit and good karma for their ancestors, and contributed to their salvation.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 忠实/忠诚：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 合作：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 独立/创造性/自由：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 节制/节俭：

— 是

Notes: This is a key virtue that is strongly emphasized as it is part of the idea of "knowing sufficiency" (zhizu 知足), which is articulated in the Daodejing.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 忍耐力/刚毅/耐心：

— 是

Notes: The virtue of yieldingness and femininity could be considered to include elements of fortitude and patience as it is based on non-contention and eventual success through stillness.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 勤奋/自律/卓越：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 果敢/果断/自信/主动：

— 否

Notes: Because they are the opposites of Chongxuan's primary virtues, these traits are actively rejected and regarded negatively.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 强壮（身体的）：

— 否

Notes: Because they are the opposites of Chongxuan's primary virtues, these traits are actively rejected and regarded negatively.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 权力/地位/高贵：

— 否

Notes: Because they are the opposites of Chongxuan's primary virtues, these traits are actively rejected and regarded negatively.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 谦卑/谦虚：

— 是

Notes: These virtues are highly valued and encouraged, particularly in Cheng Xuanying's commentary on the Daodejing.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 满足/恬静/平和：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 愉悦/激情/开心：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 乐观/希望：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 感恩/答谢：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 尊敬/敬畏/赞叹：

— 是

Notes: Although this may be less emphasized for humans, accounts in which a deity preaches (for example, in Benji jing), all those listening are described as feeling reverence, awe, and wonder.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 信仰/信念/信任/信奉：

— 是

Notes: For instance, Chongxuan texts (such as Cheng Xuanying's writings and the Benji jing) emphasize "taking refuge in the Dao," a mirroring of the Buddhist idea of "taking refuge in the Buddha," which implies that one must have faith in the salvific and compassionate power of the Dao (Assandri 2009, 216).

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 智慧/理解力：

— 是

Notes: Wisdom is endorsed especially as "real wisdom," which enables the adept eventually to realize Dao. This is opposed to "expedient wisdom" which is the wisdom needed to function in the world and to convert human beings. Expedient wisdom is thus worldly wisdom, which serves for life in the world, but is not immediately relevant for spiritual cultivation.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 洞察力/聪颖：

— 是

Notes: Intelligence is valued as an innate capacity for understanding, and for being able to grasp the teachings of a master or of Dao. In this sense, it is called "sharp faculty" (ligen 利根). However, discernment in the sense of a knowledge of external things, knowledge of the world, which discriminates in a dualistic fashion between good and evil, beautiful and ugly etc., is rejected (see for example Daode jing chapters 3, 10, 53 and Cheng Xuanying's commentary to them).

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 美丽/魅力：

— 否

Notes: Beauty is understood as part of a pair of values (along with ugliness) that relativize and thus mutually eliminate one another. In other words, there can be beauty only in contrast to ugliness and vice versa. This point is stated explicitly in the "Inner Chapters" of the Zhuangzi and in chapter 2 of the Daodejing.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ (身体的) 干净/整齐：

— 否

Notes: While the Chongxuan texts we have do not specifically elaborate on cleanliness or orderliness, it should be noted that Chongxuan thinkers were ordained Daoists, and Daoist monastic rules had much to say about cleanliness and orderliness. (See sections 9 and 10 of Kohn 2004, where regulations regarding clothing and housing of Daoist priests are described, including rules for cleanliness.)

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 宗教团体宣扬其他的重要美德：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

常规

会员费用和惯例

该宗教团体要求成员禁欲(完全禁绝性生活)吗：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

该宗教团体要求成员节制性行为(部分禁止性生活)吗：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

该宗教团体要求成员阉割吗：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

该宗教团体要求成员斋戒吗：

— 未知领域

Notes: Chongxuan texts being mainly philosophical discussions, they do not speak about fasting. However, the Tang dynasty Daoist Monastic Manual Fengdao kejie yingshi (translated in Kohn 2004) might give us some indications, and there we find fasting in preparation of purgation rituals mentioned (Kohn 2004, 77). We do, however, know comparatively little about fasting in medieval Daoist Monasteries.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

该宗教团体要求成员断除某些食物（对想吃的食物的禁忌）吗：

— 未知领域

Notes: Chongxuan texts being mainly philosophical discussions, they do not speak about fasting. However, the Tang dynasty Daoist Monastic Manual Fengdao kejie yingshi (translated in Kohn 2004) might give us some indications, and there we find prohibitions against ordaining “meat-eaters” and people who drink alcohol (Kohn 2004, 107), which might indicate that meat and alcohol were not allowed to Daoist monastics at the time. We do, however, know comparatively little about dietary prescriptions for medieval Daoist monastics.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

该宗教团体要求成员在身体上留下永久性疤痕或作疼痛的修整吗：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

该宗教团体要求成员忍受疼痛的身体姿势或暂时性的伤口吗：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

该宗教团体要求成年成员的牺牲生命吗

“成年”在此指该文化中主位或本土的类别；如果此类别不同于主流西方定义中的超过18周岁的并且为他/她的行为负法律责任的人类，那么请在评论/来源中注明：以下文本框。

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

该宗教团体要求儿童成员的牺牲吗

“儿童”在此指该文化中主位或本土的类别；如果此类别不同于主流西方定义，请在评论/来源中注明：以下文本框。

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

该宗教团体要求成员自我牺牲（自杀）吗：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

该宗教团体要求成员贡献出财产／昂贵的物品吗：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

该宗教团体要求成员奉献出自己的时间吗（例如参加会议或仪式，常规祷告等）：

— 是

Notes: In addition to contemplative and meditative practices, Daoists living in monasteries and temples participated in regular ritual practices such as scripture readings and prayers. As well, Daoists could be invited to participate in large-scale rituals at the palace, which could last for days. As Chongxuan Daoists lived in monasteries in the capital, it is safe to assume that they participated in these various rites.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

该宗教团体要求成员承受身体上的风险吗：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

该宗教团体要求成员接受道德戒律吗：

— 是

Notes: Daoists would accept ritual precepts at their formal ordination. This is mentioned also in Chongxuan scriptures like Cheng Xuanying's Commentary to the Daode jing or the Benji jing.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

成为该宗教团体的成员会被组外成员边缘化吗：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

该宗教团体要求成员参与小规模宗教仪式（私人的，家庭的）吗：

— 是

Notes: In addition to contemplative and meditative practices, Daoists living in monasteries and temples participated in regular ritual practices such as scripture readings and prayers as well as more elaborate rituals designed to benefit the empire or the emperor.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 表演间的平均时间间隔是多少（以小时计）：

这里表演指小型仪式。

— 未知领域

Notes: The Tang dynasty Daoist Monastic manual Fengdao kejie yingshi, translated by Livia Kohn, speaks of morning and evening audience rituals (Kohn 2004, 151) and a noon purgation (Kohn 2004, 157). Presumably, these were held daily in the monasteries. We do not know for sure what other rituals were held between these morning and evening rituals. Furthermore, we do not know if this Daoist Monastic Manual represents actual conditions or, more plausibly, is to be read as a normative text, which however not necessarily reflects conditions and practices in the monasteries.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

该宗教团体要求成员参与大规模的宗教仪式吗：

比如，涉及两个或以上的家庭；包括有大规模的“典礼”和“节庆”。

一是

Notes: In addition to the potentially large scale practices within Daoist monasteries, Daoists in the capital were frequently called upon by the emperor to conduct rituals of general salvation or for the protection of the state, which could be very large.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 平均来说，大规模的宗教仪式有多少参与者聚集在一个地点：

— 我不知道

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 表演间的平均时间间隔是多少（以小时计）：

这里表演指小型仪式。

— 我不知道

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 是否存在正统性审查：

正统性审查是用于保证用常规方式阐释仪式的机制。比如，通过专业祭司或者其他系统的管理的显赫监督，诉诸于详细适当阐释的文本等等。

— 我不知道

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 是否存在对仪轨规范性审查：

仪轨规范性审查是用于保证用常规方式阐释仪式的机制。比如，通过专业祭司或者其他系统的管理的显赫监督，诉诸于详细记载适当程序的文本等等。

— 我不知道

Notes: Correct execution of ritual is an area of major concern for Daoists, because the rituals establish communication between the Daoists and powerful deities, mistakes in the execution of rituals might endanger all possible benefits the rituals intend to offer. Therefore the matter is taken very seriously, and we find very detailed instructions for rituals in many Daoist texts. Since Chongxuan refers to a philosophical trend, we find little ritual instructions in the Chongxuan texts. However, since the proponents of Chongxuan teachings were regularly ordained Daoists, we can be sure they also participated in rituals, for which generally detailed descriptions of the relevant procedures existed and were carefully followed.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 参与包括完全同步的修行吗：

— 我不知道

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 使用酒精饮料吗：

— 否

Notes: Chongxuan texts do not mention intoxicants, except wine in a negative context. Daoist scriptures from the early medieval period seem to frown on the consumption of alcohol (Kohn 2004, 78).

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

除了仪式之外还有群内的的标示性符号吗：

比如，关于外表的特别改变，比如割礼、纹身、牺牲等等。

— 是

Notes: As discussed in the Daoist Monastic Manual (Kohn 2004), ordained Daoists wore ritual vestments and headgear that distinguished them from other people.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 纹身/身体上疤痕等：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 割礼：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 饮食禁忌：

— 未知领域

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 头发：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 装束：

— 是

Notes: As discussed in the Daoist Monastic Manual (Kohn 2004), ordained Daoists wore ritual vestments and headgear that distinguished them from other people.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 装饰物

— 是

Notes: As discussed in the Daoist Monastic Manual (Kohn 2004), ordained Daoists wore ritual vestments and headgear that distinguished them from other people.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 古老的用于仪式的语言：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 其它：

— 是: Headgear

Notes: See the specific descriptions in Kohn 2004.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

团体使用虚拟的亲族称谓吗：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

社会与机构

社会复杂程度

对宗教团体所属社会最恰当的描述为（请选其一）：

— 一个帝国

Notes: Chongxuan Daoism developed with the capitals of the Northern and Southern Dynasties, as well as the Sui and Tang empires. The former were contending polities that divided the Yellow and Yangzi Rivers region while the latter were centralized empires that arose when the northern polities conquered the south.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

福利

该宗教团体提供制度化的救助饥荒的服务吗：

— 否

Notes: In general, Chongxuan teachings and their theorists were oriented towards theological issues and debates, not institutional concerns. As such, most of the questions in this section do not apply.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

饥荒救济是通过该宗教团体以外的机构提供给该团体信众的吗：

— 是

Notes: The state provided famine relief.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

该宗教团体提供制度化的的贫困救济吗：

— 否

Notes: In general, Chongxuan teachings and their theorists were oriented towards theological issues and debates, not institutional concerns. As such, most of the questions in this section do not apply.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

贫困救济是通过该宗教团体以外的机构提供给该团体信众的吗：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

该宗教团体对年老体弱者有制度化的关怀吗：

— 否

Notes: Little is known about Daoism and institutional welfare for this period, though there are scattered references in ritual texts that masters should use the money they receive as offerings in order to help the poor and elderly.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

对年老体弱者制度化的关怀是通过该宗教团体以外的机构提供给该团体信众的吗：

— 是

Notes: In general, the care of the elder and infirm was the responsibility of the family, but the state also at times helped and supported the elderly (Benn 2002, 262).

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

教育

该宗教团体为信众提供正规教育吗：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 正规教育仅限于宗教专职人员吗：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 男性和女性都能得到这种教育吗：

— 是

Notes: Although there appear to be no Chongxuan texts that were written by women, Daoists did maintain nunneries and nuns were educated. For more, see Kohn 2004, 64-65, and Hinsch 2020, 79-80.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

正规教育是通过宗教团体以外的机构提供给团体信众的吗：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 男性和女性都能得到宗教团体以外的教育吗：

— 否

Notes: In Tang dynasty, women of the aristocracy often received an education, and there are many examples of learned women. While there were texts specifically for women, and a study curriculum for women, it seems that women had to be educated at home, they were not permitted into institutionalized schools, nor did they get access to the official examination system. (Cf. Hinsch 2020, 91-106)

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

官僚机构

团体的信徒与团体内的官方机构有互动吗？

— 是

Notes: Because it was institutionalized on the Buddhist model (meaning monasteries structured by hierarchical priesthoods), Daoism included an internal bureaucracy with which its adherents interacted. Chongxuan developed within this greater context and Chongxuan theorists were ordained Daoist priests and, thus, held positions within that bureaucracy.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

宗教信众与其他官僚机构有互动吗：

— 是

Notes: Since they resided mostly in the capital, Chongxuan Daoists interacted with the imperial bureaucracy.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

公共工程

该宗教团体储备公共食品吗：

— 否

Notes: In general, Chongxuan teachings and their theorists were oriented towards theological issues and debates, not institutional concerns. As such, most of the questions in this section do not apply.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

公共食品储备是通过该宗教团体以外的机构提供给该团体信众的吗：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

该宗教团体提供水资源管理（灌溉、防洪）吗：

— 否

Notes: In general, Chongxuan teachings and their theorists were oriented towards theological issues and debates, not institutional concerns. As such, most of the questions in this section do not apply.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

水资源管理是通过该宗教团体以外的机构提供给该团体信众的吗：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

该宗教团体提供基础设施吗：

— 否

Notes: In general, Chongxuan teachings and their theorists were oriented towards theological issues and debates, not institutional concerns. As such, most of the questions in this section do not apply.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

基础设施是通过该宗教团体以外的机构提供给团体信众的吗：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

纳税

该宗教团体课取税款或什一税吗：

— 否

Notes: In general, Chongxuan teachings and their theorists were oriented towards theological issues and debates, not institutional concerns. As such, most of the questions in this section do not apply. We might note that early Daoists asked for a tithe of five bushels of rice (hence the name Five Bushels of Rice Sect for the heavenly Master's movement). However, this practice seems to have subsided in the course of time, at least it does not seem to have been practiced in the temples in Chang'an where Chongxuan thinkers resided. These temples were financed by imperial patronage.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

团体信众的税是由该宗教团体以外的机构来征收吗：

— 否

Notes: Daoist temples were open to anyone who might wish to participate and pray to deities. If these participants were normal citizens, they would, of course, be subject to state taxation. However, the religious professionals living in Daoist monasteries were, like their Buddhist counterparts, exempt from taxation. Because the "adherents" of the Chongxuan teaching were all ordained Daoists, they belonged to the latter category of tax-exempt individuals.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

强制

该宗教团体设有体制化的警务部门吗：

— 否

Notes: In general, Chongxuan teachings and their theorists were oriented towards theological issues and debates, not institutional concerns. As such, most of the questions in this section do not apply.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

宗教团体的信众与外部体制下的警务部门有互动吗：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

该宗教团体设置体制化的法官吗：

— 否

Notes: In general, Chongxuan teachings and their theorists were oriented towards theological issues and debates, not institutional concerns. As such, most of the questions in this section do not apply.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

宗教团体的信众与外部体制下的司法系统有互动吗：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

该宗教团体施加制度化的处罚吗：

— 否

Notes: In general, Chongxuan teachings and their theorists were oriented towards theological issues and debates, not institutional concerns. As such, most of the questions in this section do not apply.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

宗教团体的信众承受宗教团体以外的体制下的处罚吗:

— 是

Notes: The Tang Dynasty had a specific law code for Buddhist and Daoist clerics, which was separate from the regular law, but was enforced by the state (Jia 2018, 3-4).

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 制度化的处罚包括死刑吗：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 制度化的处罚包括流放吗：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 制度化的处罚包括体罚吗：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 制度化的处罚包括排挤孤立吗：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

↳ 制度化的处罚包括没收财产吗:

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

该宗教团体有正式的法典吗：

— 否

Notes: In general, Chongxuan teachings and their theorists were oriented towards theological issues and debates, not institutional concerns. As such, most of the questions in this section do not apply. The Tang dynasty had a formal legal code for Buddhist and Daoists, the Daoseng ge 道僧格 (Jia 2018, 4, no.11).

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

宗教团体的信众受制于外部体制下的法典吗：

— 是

Notes: The Tang dynasty had a formal legal code for Buddhist and Daoists, the Daoseng ge 道僧格 (Jia 2018, 4, no.11).

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

福利

该宗教团体有体制化的军事力量吗：

— 否

Notes: In general, Chongxuan teachings and their theorists were oriented towards theological issues and debates, not institutional concerns. As such, most of the questions in this section do not apply.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

宗教团体的信众参加宗教团体以外机构提供的机制化的军事力量吗：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

宗教团体的信众受保护或受治于宗教图案以外机构提供的机制化的军事力量吗：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

书面语

该宗教团体有自己独特的书面语吗：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

团体信众能在宗教团体以外的体制中接触到非宗教专用的书面语吗：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

团体信众在宗教团体以外的体制下使用使用非宗教专用的书面语吗：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

日历

该宗教团体有正式的历法吗：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

该宗教团体的信众在宗教团体以外的体制下有正式的历法可用吗：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

食物生产

该宗教团体自产食物吗

— 否

Notes: In general, Chongxuan teachings and their theorists were oriented towards theological issues and debates, not institutional concerns. As such, most of the questions in this section do not apply.

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

该宗教团体外的机构向团体信众提供食物吗：

一是

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

请描述食物生产的形式/层级【多选】

—我不知道

Specific to this answer:

参与者的状态 ✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

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